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Oral Presentations

O3_02

SMARTWATER project implementation in the period 2021-2024 and smart management of land and water resources in BiH agriculture

Mihajlo Marković^{1*}, Đurađ Hajder¹, Milan Šipka¹, Mladen Todorović², Nery Zapata³,
Teresa A. Paço⁴, Erminio E. Riezzo⁵, Sabrija Čadro⁶

¹ *University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Agriculture, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina*

² *Centro Internazionale di Alti Studi Agronomici Mediterranei, CIHEAM Bari, Valenzano, Italy*

³ *Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas, Madrid, Spain*

⁴ *Universidade de Lisboa, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, LEAF, TERRA, Lisbon, Portugal*

⁵ *SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL, Roma, Italy*

⁶ *University of Sarajevo, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Science, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina*

* *Corresponding author: Mihajlo Marković mihajlo.markovic@agro.unibl.org*

Abstract

Horizon 2020 project “*Promoting SMART agricultural WATER management in Bosnia and Herzegovina*” (SMARTWATER) started in 2021. This was the first time that an academic institution from Bosnia and Herzegovina is coordinating a Horizon 2020 project. The main objective of SMARTWATER is to reinforce networking, research and S&T cooperation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), the University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other connected national institutions, in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and to increase their competency and fund-raising skills for a successful participation in the European Union Research Programs. Main project topics include: 1) cloud-based smart technologies, 2) new generation of satellite remote sensing data, 3) water-energy-food nexus and 4) climate change impact on agriculture. In the period 2021-2024 project consortium organized 3 advanced training courses, 3 summer schools, joint research activities (experiments) in 3 years and at 2 locations in BiH, 3 stakeholders’ meetings (roundtables), 3 post-graduate MSc courses, 13 mutual staff exchanges, 3 hands-on workshops on R&I and worked on the development of 2 smart water management tools and smart national strategies in agriculture. Project teams’ members attended more than 20 international conferences and published 15 academic papers in three abovementioned topics (<https://zenodo.org/search?q=smartwater&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>). SMARTWATER activities are being disseminated on a regular basis at the official website (<https://www.smartwater-project.eu/>) and social media profiles (Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn and YouTube). SMARTWATER consortium will organize an international workshop in BiH (Trebinje, May 29-30) so we call all interested stakeholders to visit our sites and to join the SMARTWATER network.

Key words: twinning, sustainability, maize, dissemination, publications

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